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Impact of oxidized carbon nanotubes on the mechanical, thermal, and hygric properties of Portland cement- and magnesium oxychloride cement-based mortars: A route to advanced building composites

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ABSTRACT

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have gained attention as nano-reinforcement for cementitious materials due to their exceptional mechanical, thermal, and self-sensing properties. While extensively studied in Portland cement (PC) composites, their application in magnesium oxychloride cement (MOC) remains underexplored. However, challenges such as CNTs agglomeration and MOC's moisture susceptibility limit their effectiveness. This study investigates the impact of oxidized multi-walled carbon nanotubes (CNTox) on the mechanical strength, durability, and water resistance of MOC, with PC composites included for comparison. Two sets of PC- and MOC-based samples were prepared and analyzed in detail, focusing on elemental composition, phase composition, fracture surface microstructure, mechanical properties, thermal, and hygric properties. The results indicate that low CNTox concentrations enhance mechanical strength and retard water ingress. In MOC composites containing 0.1 wt% of CNTox, an 8.4 % increase in compressive strength, a 14.0 % enhancement in flexural strength, and a 0.5 % increase in Young's modulus were recorded. In PC-based composites, the addition of CNTox led to an improvement in flexural strength by 10.6–20.0 %, while the maximum compressive strength increased by up to 50 % in the composite with 0.05 wt% of CNTox. Thermal conductivity and heat storage increased in all composites containing CNTox. Furthermore, the moisture resistance of CNTox-reinforced MOC composites improved by approximately 1.9–21.4 % compared to the control mix. The results highlight the potential of CNTox as an effective nanoadditive for enhancing the properties of cement-based construction materials.

1. Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs), owing to their one-dimensional tubular architecture, are distinguished by superior mechanical

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characteristics, elevated electrical conductivity, piezoelectric effects, and exceptional thermal performance [1–3]. Based on the number of atomic layers, CNTs are categorized into single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNT) and multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) [4,5]. They exhibit low density, a high aspect ratio, nanoscale diameters, and remarkable chemical stability [6,7]. Consequently, CNTs hold significant potential to substantially enhance the mechanical properties of PC-based materials and concrete under both static and dynamic loads at the nano/micro level and macro scale [8]. The integration of MWCNTs into cementitious composites can result in notable augmentation of compressive strength, flexural strength, and Young's modulus [9]. It was previously proven that the addition of nanofillers can effectively modify the interfacial bond strength and microstructure, leading into increase in the mechanical parameters [10]. The microstructure modification is well connected with the nano-core effect, resulting in an increased formation of the cementitious products [11]. The incorporation of CNTs into cementitious composites significantly enhances their mechanical properties. Studies have shown substantial improvements in compressive strength, tensile strength, ductility, and fatigue resistance. For instance, Raki et al. reported a 50 % increase in compressive strength of self-sensing cementitious composites modified with MWCNTs [12,13]. Li et al. observed an 18 % improvement in static compressive strength and a 43 % increase in fatigue strength due to the improved pore structure and crack-bridging effects of CNTs with varying sizes and surface modifications [14]. Huang et al. further documented enhancements in flexural fatigue life and fatigue strength by 195 % and 31.4 %, respectively [15], while Abdulkadir et al. demonstrated improved tensile strength and ductility in strain-hardening composites with CNTs admixing [16]. Beyond mechanical reinforcement, CNTs influence the microstructural and hydration properties of cementitious materials. Due to their hollow tubular structure, CNTs provide additional nucleation sites for cement hydration products, accelerating the formation of early-age hydration phases and reducing the thickness of the interfacial transition zone between fillers and the cement matrix. This refined microstructure limits microcrack formation and propagation, ultimately reinforcing the composite material [17–19]. Furthermore, CNTs enhance self-healing capabilities by facilitating the transport of water and reactive substances to crack locations, aiding autonomous repair mechanisms within the cement matrix [16,20].

CNTs are extensively employed in conferring self-sensing capabilities to construction materials, facilitating the detection of parameters such as vibration, strain, stress, shrinkage, damage, structural health, and fatigue [19–24]. The heat storage function of cement composites integrated with CNTs and phase change microcapsules has been the subject of a recent investigation by Xie et al. [25]. In this study, the high thermal conductivity of CNTs facilitated rapid phase transition. However, the effective use of CNTs in cementitious composites requires careful control of their dispersion and concentration. CNTs tend to agglomerate due to strong van der Waals forces and their hydrophobic nature, which negatively affects the workability and fluidity of fresh cement mixtures [26–29]. As a result, CNT content is typically limited to between 0.05 and 1.0 wt% relative to cement, which can restrict performance gains, particularly in self-sensing applications [30]. Exceeding this optimal range can lead to reduced mechanical properties due to nanoparticle agglomeration and interfacial sliding among CNT bundles [7,30–33].

Most of the research concerning the incorporation of carbon-based nanomaterials for the purpose of enhancing the durability and engineering properties of building materials has predominantly focused on PC-based composites and concrete. The exploration of nanomodification in materials formed from alternative matrices has been limited. Recently, investigations into the nano-reinforcement and nano-enhancement of magnesium oxychloride cement (MOC) composites [34,35], as well as polymer-based composites [36,37], have emerged; however, this area of study remains incomplete and warrants further examination. In this context, the investigation of the impact of incorporating multiwalled oxidized carbon nanotubes (CNTox) into MOC mortars was undertaken, with an emphasis on the effect of varying dosages of CNTox and identification of optimal CNTox content. CNTox were chosen due to their content of oxygen-containing groups, which make them easier to disperse in the aqueous suspensions of raw materials used for the preparation of the designed composites compared to CNTs. The dispersion of CNTs is harder due to their increased hydrophobic nature, resulting in the formation of large bundles and agglomerates, which form weak spots in the microstructure of the resulting composite. [38] For comparative purposes, PC-based mortars enhanced through the incorporation of CNTox were also explored.

MOC offers several advantages over traditional PC, such as higher early and ultimate strength, low alkalinity, excellent fire and abrasion resistance, low shrinkage, and a significantly lower carbon footprint [39]. These make it a promising alternative to PC, offering application in industrial flooring, prefabricated elements, passive fire protection systems, repairs, claddings, etc. Despite its promising performance, MOC's main limitation is its sensitivity to water. However, recent studies demonstrate that this drawback can be effectively mitigated by incorporating nanoadditives, which may improve water resistance and enable crack-bridging [40].

The microstructural, macrostructural, mechanical, hygric, and thermal characteristics of the hardened composites underwent extensive experimental evaluation. Additionally, acknowledging the susceptibility of the MOC matrix to moisture degradation, its durability in relation to water exposure was assessed. The selection of oxidized MWCNT, or surface-modified nanotubes, was premised on the fact that the untreated CNT's smooth and inert surfaces contribute to relatively weak interfacial bonding between the CNTs and the inorganic matrix. The studies [7,41,42] reported that the oxidation process of CNTs effectively alters their surface, thereby enhancing their dispersion. This research endeavors to enhance the current understanding of the nanomodification of MOC composites while aiming to augment their functional attributes and durability.

2. Materials and experimental methods

2.1. Materials and sample preparation

PC mortars were prepared from CEM I 42.5 R (Heidelberg Materials CZ, Czech Republic), silica sand (Filtrační písky, s.r.o., Czech Republic), and batch water. Portland cement (PC) used adhered to EN 197–1 [43], and its oxide composition, as analyzed by X-ray fluorescence (XRF), is depicted in Fig. 1. The essential physical characteristics of the utilized PC are as follows: specific density of

3129 kg·m⁻³, Blaine fineness of 381 m²·kg⁻¹, and soundness of 0.8 mm. Silica sand was a mix of three sand fractions PG1, PG2, and PG3 having particles in the range 0–0.5 mm, 0.5–1.0 mm, and 1.0–2.0 mm, respectively. The water-to-cement ratio was set at 0.5, in accordance with EN 196–1 [44].

For the synthesis of MOC-based samples, MgO (Penta s.r.o., Czech Republic), MgCl₂·6 H₂O of p.a. purity (Lach-ner, s.r.o., Czech Republic), silica sand (Filtrační písky, s.r.o., Czech Republic) in the three above-mentioned size fractions, and tap water were used. MgO powder had a specific density of 3459 kg·m⁻³ and a LOI of max. 5.0 wt%. Except for MgO (93.43 wt%), the magnesia powder comprised Al₂O₃ (5.98 wt%), SiO₂ (0.31 wt%), CaO (0.08 wt%), Cl (0.08 wt%), and SO₃ (0.06 wt%). Additional impurities, including Br, As₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, and Cr₂O₃, were present only in trace quantities.

For nano-enhancement of samples, commercially purchased oxidized multi-walled carbon nanotubes (CNTox) (Chengdu Organic Chemicals Co. Ltd., China) were used. CNTox possessed purity > 95 %. An average outer diameter, inner diameter, and length of CNTox were 2–8 nm, 2–5 nm, and 10–30 μm, respectively.

The composition of the samples prepared is shown in Tables 1 and 2. MOC-REF and PC-REF serve as reference mixtures devoid of CNTox. Samples inclusive of CNTox are identified as MOC-CNTox-X and PC-CNTox-X, where X denotes the percentage by weight (wt %) of the nanomaterial relative to the weight of the corresponding binder. The content of CNTox was set in order to obtain as good material properties, while maintaining good dispersion of this nanoadditive in the sample matrix regarding our previous research. [45, 46]

Preparation, casting, and curing of PC samples went by the following order: CNTox were dispersed in tap water (Fig. 2) for 5 min at 10,000 rpm using high-shear mixer Ultra-Turrax T-18 (IKA, Germany), equipped with the S18N-19G dispersing element (19 mm diameter). This setup is suitable to process the liquid in volumes from 0.01 to 1.5 L at a maximum speed up to 25,000 rpm, providing stable shear forces for uniform dispersion of CNTox in nanomaterial suspension. The dispersion was performed for a duration of 5 min at 10,000 rpm at stable laboratory temperature (23 ± 2 °C). This suspension was mixed with PC in a planetary mortar mixer (ELE, United Kingdom). Silica sand was incorporated after 30 s of mixing, followed by an additional 60 s of mechanical mixing, subsequent manual mixing, and a final 3-minute period of mixing in the mortar mixer. Fresh mortars were poured into molds of 40 mm × 40 mm × 160 mm, demolded after 24 h, and cured for the next 27 days in the climatic chamber (temperature of (23 ± 2) °C and relative humidity of (90 ± 5) %). The chamber's environmental conditions were continuously monitored and controlled to ensure consistent curing throughout the curing period.

Preparation, casting, and curing of MOC samples went by the following procedure: The MgCl₂·6 H₂O was diluted in tap water. This solution was employed to disperse CNTox using an Ultra Turrax T-18 (IKA, Germany) for 5 min at 10,000 rpm. The resulting suspension/clear solution of MgCl₂ was subsequently combined with MgO in a planetary mortar mixer (ELE, United Kingdom) in accordance with the prescribed mixing protocol. The addition of silica sand and further mixing was carried out in the same way as in the case of PC samples. The fresh mixtures were cast into 40 mm × 40 mm × 160 mm molds, removed after 24 h, and then air-cured in a climatic chamber at a temperature of (23 ± 2) °C and a relative humidity of (50 ± 5) % for 27 days.

While preparing the samples, the components were weighed using an accurate laboratory scale with an uncertainty of 0.01 g.

2.2. Characterization techniques

Laser diffraction was used to measure particle size distribution curves of MgO and PC. Sieve analysis was performed to obtain grain size curves of silica sand. To determine the chemical composition of both binders, X-ray fluorescence (XRF) was used. CNTox were characterized by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to determine the microstructure.

The phase composition of the cured samples was characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD). To ascertain the chemical composition, the XRF technique was employed. The microstructure of the hardened composites was examined through optical microscopy

Fig. 1. Chemical composition of PC (wt%) obtained by XRF.

Table 1

Composition of tested PC-based samples.

Mixture ID	Mass (g)			
	PC	H ₂ O	Sand	CNTox
PC-REF	900	450	3 × 900	0
PC-CNTox-0.05	900	450	3 × 900	0.68
PC-CNTox-0.1	900	450	3 × 900	1.35
PC-CNTox-0.5	900	450	3 × 900	6.75
PC-CNTox-1.0	900	450	3 × 900	13.50

Table 2

Composition of tested MOC-based samples.

Mixture ID	Mass (g)				
	MgO	MgCl ₂ ·6 H ₂ O	H ₂ O	Sand	CNTox
MOC-REF	700	706.19	438.03	3 × 700	0
MOC-CNTox-0.05	700	706.19	438.03	3 × 700	0.92
MOC-CNTox-0.1	700	706.19	438.03	3 × 700	1.84
MOC-CNTox-0.5	700	706.19	438.03	3 × 700	9.20
MOC-CNTox-1.0	700	706.19	438.03	3 × 700	18.40

Fig. 3. Cured samples prepared for testing: PC-based (left), MOC-based (right).

(OM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and mercury intrusion porosimetry (MIP). Elemental mapping of the fracture surface was conducted utilizing energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS). Mechanical properties, including compressive and flexural strength as well as Young's dynamic modulus, were evaluated. Furthermore, hygric parameters such as the 24-hour water absorption and water absorption coefficient were determined. Heat transport and storage parameters were investigated using a nonstationary heat pulse apparatus functioning on the hot disk principle. In the case of MOC composites, the water resistance was characterized through the assessment of the softening coefficient. The analytical methods employed are expounded upon in greater detail in our previous

publication [47]. The outlined research methodology implemented in this study is shown in Fig. 4.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of raw materials

The microstructure of CNTox was characterized using SEM and TEM. As illustrated in Fig. 5, the CNTox exhibit a network of entangled, fibrous structures with predominantly random tube orientation. The tubes manifest an average thickness of ~ 30 nm. Careful analysis of the micrographs reveals morphological features consistent with oxidative etching, including surface roughness, wall thinning, and isolated hole-like defects or irregular tube ends. Several nanotubes appear fractured, with rough or jagged termini, indicative of oxidative damage and partial fragmentation. These features, clearly visible in the provided images, align with well-documented effects of oxidative treatment on carbon nanotubes—namely, increased defect density and structural weakening.

Fig. 6 presents the particle size of the binders and silica sand determined by sieve analysis for silica sand and LD for the binders. The MgO powder demonstrates a significantly finer particle size compared to the PC, with particle size distribution parameters d_{90} , d_{50} , and d_{10} of $8.13 \mu\text{m}$, $2.41 \mu\text{m}$, and $0.84 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. The particle size distribution parameters for PC were documented as $38.32 \mu\text{m}$, $25.64 \mu\text{m}$, and $8.68 \mu\text{m}$. The particle size range of silica sand varied from 0 to $2 \mu\text{m}$, which is consistent with the data provided by the sand supplier.

The prepared cement beams were fractured, and their fracture surfaces were analyzed using optical microscopy (Fig. 7). In both PC (marked in blue) and MOC (marked in green) composites, silica sand particles (marked in yellow) were uniformly distributed throughout the matrix. Although the presence of oxygen functional groups on carbon nanotubes is expected to reduce their hydrophobicity, they predominantly appear as agglomerates (marked in red) in the MOC sample set. However, as the CNTox content increases, these agglomerates become less visible due to the overall pigmentation of the matrix. In the PC-based samples, the agglomerates are also not as easily distinguishable, likely due to the inherently grey color of the PC matrix.

For the elemental analysis of the samples, XRF was used. The results of the elemental compositions are presented in the Supporting Information file as Table SI 1 and Table SI 2. As expected, the PC sample set primarily consists of calcium, silicon, and carbon, along with light elements that XRF cannot detect. Similarly, the MOC sample set is mainly composed of carbon, light elements, magnesium, silicon, and chlorine. The only impurity detected was iron, most likely introduced from the milling bowl. As the elemental composition of the samples does not significantly change with the increasing amount of CNTox, Fig. 8 shows the composition in pie charts for better clarity.

The XRD patterns are shown in Fig. 9. In the PC sample set, the phase composition remains unchanged with increasing CNTox content. All PC samples contain ettringite, quartz, portlandite, calcite, alite, and gypsum. Similarly, in the MOC sample set, the phase composition does not change with increasing CNTox content. The only detected phases in these samples are quartz (SiO_2) and MOC phase 5 ($\text{Mg}_3(\text{OH})_5\text{Cl} \cdot 8 \text{H}_2\text{O}$).

Fig. 4. Flow chart of the conducted research.

Fig. 5. Micrographs of CNTox by TEM (left) and SEM (right).

Fig. 6. Particle size distribution of silica sand (left) and binders (right).

The SEM micrographs of the PC sample set (Fig. 10, left) reveal a heterogeneous microstructure with distinct cement hydration products. The micrographs showcase a dense cementitious matrix interspersed with needle-like and plate-like structures, likely corresponding to ettringite and portlandite crystals. The CNTox may appear as fibers or entangled structures within the matrix. Where visible, the CNTox bundle-rich regions are marked at the micrographs. The surface texture suggests a well-hydrated system, with the CNTox potentially enhancing the packing density and reducing porosity. The image also exhibits voids and cracks, which could indicate shrinkage effects or incomplete densification.

The SEM micrographs of the MOC sample set (Fig. 10, right) reveal a well-developed crystalline microstructure. The micrograph predominantly features large, plate-like, or needle-like formations, characteristic of phase 5, which is a primary hydration product in MOC. The matrix appears dense, with CNTox likely embedded within the structure, potentially enhancing mechanical interlocking and bridging microcracks. The micrograph also shows regions with finer textures that belong to silica sand particles.

EDS was used to analyze the elemental composition of all samples (Fig. SI 1 and Fig. SI 2). In the PC sample set, the elements are evenly distributed throughout the samples. In contrast, the MOC sample set exhibits a distinct pattern where CNTox tends to cluster in bundles. This pattern becomes more visible as the CNTox concentration increases.

The macrostructural characteristics of 28-day composites are detailed together with their expanded combined uncertainties in Table 3. The data provided on bulk density, specific density, and open porosity reflect the average values derived from four samples. The incorporation of CNTox facilitated an increase in the bulk density of PC composites, consequently reducing their porosity in comparison to the control material PC-REF. This enhancement can be attributed to the improved packing of the input materials and forming nucleation sites for PC hydrates, leading to the dense and more compacted microstructure. No discernible trend was observed in the specific density data. In this context, the differences among the composites studied were minor and not statistically significant. Quantitatively, the variations in specific density relative to that of the reference composite ranged from 0.09 % to 0.24 %.

Generally, the specific density of MOC composites diminished as the concentration of nanoadditives in the composite mixture

Fig. 7. Micrographs of all prepared samples from optical microscope.

increased. Similarly, the total open porosity was reduced when compared to the reference composites, with the extent of porosity reduction being proportional to the amount of added CNTox. The drop in porosity varied from 31.4 % measured for MOC-CNTox-1.0–1.9 % recorded for MOC-CNTox-0.05. The observed reduction in porosity can be attributed to the prevention of microcrack formation and the enhanced formation of precipitated MOC products at nucleation sites influenced by the high specific surface area of the employed CNTox.

Conversely, no discernible pattern was identified in the bulk density. Notably, composites containing up to 0.5 wt% of CNTox exhibited a reduction in bulk density, whereas composites with 0.5 % and 1.0 % dosages of the nanoadditive displayed bulk density

Fig. 8. Elemental composition of PC-REF (left) and MOC-REF (right) in wt%; light elements – elements with atomic number $z < 11$.

Fig. 9. XRD diffractograms of all prepared samples with detected phases.

values exceeding those of the reference materials MOC-REF.

The results of microstructural analysis performed by MIP are shown in Table 4. In the case of PC composites, the values of total pore volume followed the trend of total open porosity obtained by a combination of the gravimetric method and helium pycnometry. The differences in average pore diameter were not significant. Nonetheless, the nano-modified composites exhibited slightly lower average pore diameter, which documents refinement of their porous structure. This agrees with the cumulative pore size distribution curves presented in Fig. 11 a. The incorporation of CNTox led to a significant reduction in the total pore volume of MOC composites, and this reduction became increasingly noticeable with the gradual increase of nanoadditive in the material compositions being studied. The average pore size of MOC-CNTox composites was marginally higher than that of the control material MOC-REF. This was attributed to the increased volume of capillary pores within the diameter range from 0.1 to 1.0 μm , as shown in Fig. 11 b.

Figs. 12 and 13 illustrate the mechanical properties of the cured composites. For PC-based materials, introducing CNTox enhanced flexural strength due to the nanoadditive's own high flexural strength. The compressive strength and Young's modulus improved with CNTox dosages of 0.05 wt% and 0.1 wt% in relation to water and binder mass. This enhancement was attributed to the role of CNTox in composites, which caused nucleation seeding effect, prevented microcracks, and led to interlocking among hydration products and

Fig. 10. SEM micrographs of prepared samples at two different magnifications.

pore structure refinement [48–50]. Conversely, an increased dosage of nanoadditive in PC composites is reported to decrease workability by forming agglomerates and trapping large amounts of water [51]. Consequently, in composites with higher nanoadditive content, such as 0.5 wt% and 1.0 %, a decrease in compressive strength and dynamic elastic modulus was noted, consistent with findings from Wang et al. [52].

Aside from materials based on PC, there is a lack of direct evidence of correlation between the enhancing effects of CNTox and their increasing dosage, which results in varying optimal contents for distinct binders and mix designs [50]. This phenomenon is observed in the studied MOC composites. An improvement in mechanical strength and Young's modulus was identified in composites with a CNTox dosage up to 0.5 wt%, with the optimal performance observed for MOC-CNTox-0.1. This observation aligns with the

Table 3
Macrostructural parameters of composites.

Material	Bulk density	Specific density	Open porosity
	ρ_b kg·m ⁻³	ρ_s kg·m ⁻³	φ %
PC-REF	2039.4 ± 28.6	2494.0 ± 34.9	18.2 ± 0.4
PC-CNTox-0.05	2066.0 ± 28.9	2500.4 ± 30.0	17.4 ± 0.4
PC-CNTox-0.1	2043.5 ± 28.6	2497.9 ± 30.0	18.1 ± 0.4
PC-CNTox-0.5	2069.7 ± 29.0	2491.8 ± 29.9	16.9 ± 0.3
PC-CNTox-1.0	2047.0 ± 28.7	2496.6 ± 30.0	18.0 ± 0.4
MOC-REF	2034.9 ± 28.5	2273.5 ± 27.3	10.5 ± 0.2
MOC-CNTox-0.05	2014.1 ± 28.2	2244.4 ± 26.9	10.3 ± 0.2
MOC-CNTox-0.1	2031.3 ± 28.4	2243.2 ± 26.9	9.4 ± 0.2
MOC-CNTox-0.5	2041.3 ± 28.6	2236.6 ± 26.8	8.7 ± 0.3
MOC-CNTox-1.0	2042.9 ± 28.6	2195.1 ± 30.7	7.2 ± 0.3

Table 4
Microstructural parameters of composites.

Material	Total pore volume	Average pore diameter
	cm ³ ·g ⁻¹	μm
PC-REF	0.0868	0.0245
PC-CNTox-0.05	0.0807	0.0227
PC-CNTox-0.1	0.0838	0.0236
PC-CNTox-0.5	0.0749	0.0231
PC-CNTox-1.0	0.0812	0.0243
MOC-REF	0.0839	0.0209
MOC-CNTox-0.05	0.0722	0.0211
MOC-CNTox-0.1	0.0671	0.0217
MOC-CNTox-0.5	0.0639	0.0219
MOC-CNTox-1.0	0.0593	0.0221

Fig. 11. Cumulative pore size distribution curves: a) PC composites, b) MOC composites.

enhancement of mechanical resistance noted in the PC composites; however, in contrast, a dosage of even 0.5 wt% of CNTox improved the evaluated mechanical parameters. The most significant improvements in mechanical properties were observed with an 8.4 % increase in compressive strength, a 14.0 % enhancement in flexural strength, and a mere 0.5 % increase in Young's modulus. The introduction of nano-reinforcement contributed to a reduction in porosity and a refinement of the porous structure, which mitigated microcracks and facilitated the interlocking of precipitated products that constitute the MOC microstructure. Additionally, an increase in high specific surface nucleation sites for MOC phase 5 is anticipated.

Fig. 14 presents a summary of the 24-hour water absorption data (W_{a24} , W_{a24m}). In both categories of composites, the incorporation of CNTox effectively retarded the ingress of water, which is advantageous concerning their durability. The partial hindrance in water absorption corresponds with the structural data, specifically the porosity of the composites. In addition to the reduced porosity, the

Fig. 12. Mechanical properties of 28-day PC composites.

Fig. 13. Mechanical properties of 28-day MOC composites.

hydrophobic nature of the nanoadditive employed [53] further contributed to the attenuation of moisture ingress. A similar effect on moisture ingress shows water absorption coefficient data (A_w) presented in Fig. 15. Compared to materials that facilitate fast and high-rate moisture transport [54,55], the water absorption coefficient was low, which helps to restrict moisture entry, thus reducing the MOC phase 5 decay. In the case of PC composites, the minimized water ingress partially prevents damage caused by freezing and thawing.

Given the susceptibility of MOC-based materials to moisture-induced deterioration, the softening coefficient was also evaluated. This coefficient represents the ratio between the compressive strength of samples submerged in water for 24 h, i.e., residual strength, and that of samples allowed to cure under laboratory conditions. Data pertaining to the softening coefficient s_c (%) and residual compressive strength f_{cr} (MPa) is graphed in Fig. 16. For all investigated composites, the incorporation of CNTox resulted in an increase in both the residual compressive strength and the softening coefficient, indicating enhanced durability against moisture-induced deterioration. This observation is consistent with the reduction in moisture ingress, as restricted moisture absorption mitigated the

Fig. 14. Water absorption of composites.

Fig. 15. Water absorption coefficient of composites.

risk of moisture damage. The increased densification of the nano-reinforced materials, the interlocking of hydrated products, and the bridging of the microcracks by CNTox collectively contributed to significantly improved water resistance. The MOC-CNTox material 1.0 exhibited the highest water resistance, with a softening coefficient that was 21.4 % greater than that of the reference composite. It is important to consider that the softening coefficient was derived based on the minimum reference compressive strength. In contrast, the material MOC-CNTox-0.1 demonstrated the highest residual compressive strength, exceeding that of MOC-REF by 17.4 %. Comparable enhancements in the water resistance of MOC materials using carbon-based nanoadditives, such as graphene nanoplatelets, have recently been documented by Lauermannová et al. [56].

Thermal properties of composites, namely dry thermal conductivity λ ($W\cdot m^{-1}\cdot K^{-1}$) and volumetric heat capacity c_v ($MJ\cdot m^{-3}\cdot K^{-1}$), are given in Fig. 17. The heat transfer was enhanced by two distinct factors: the reduction in composites' porosity and the increased dosage of CNTox in the composite mix. The thermal conductivity of MWCNT, whether considered individually or in bundles, is documented to span a range from 20 to 6000 $W\cdot m^{-1}\cdot K^{-1}$ [57–60], thereby making a substantial contribution to the overall thermal performance of the composites. Furthermore, it is typically observed that the thermal conductivity of oxidized carbon nanotubes is superior to that of their non-oxidized counterparts [61]. The volumetric heat capacity exhibited a similar pattern, meaning that the heat storage ability was improved by the decrease in porosity and the inclusion of CNTox. The augmentation in heat storage capacity

Fig. 16. Softening coefficient and residual compressive strength.

and the improved thermal transport capability may offer significant advantages in the design and development of construction composites targeted for thermal storage applications. For instance, a nano-enriched composite matrix could be integrated with phase change materials to facilitate latent heat storage.

4. Conclusions

This study investigated the effects of oxidized carbon nanotubes (CNTox) on the microstructure, mechanical properties, durability, and thermal behavior of magnesium oxychloride cement (MOC) and Portland cement (PC) composites. For PC composites, the incorporation of CNTox at low dosages (0.05–0.1 wt%) improved compressive strength, flexural strength, and Young’s modulus. These enhancements are attributed to CNTox’s nucleation seeding, crack-bridging effects, and pore structure refinement. However, higher CNTox contents (≥ 0.5 wt%) caused agglomeration and water entrapment, which reduced workability and mechanical performance. CNTox also contributed to reduced porosity and moisture ingress, enhancing freeze-thaw durability. Thermal conductivity and volumetric heat capacity increased moderately, suggesting improved heat transfer and storage potential. MOC composites exhibited a distinct response to CNTox addition. The nano-reinforcement effectively reduced open porosity by up to 31.4 %, with associated densification and refinement of the porous structure. Mechanical properties improved significantly up to 0.5 wt% CNTox, with optimal

Fig. 17. Thermal conductivity and volumetric heat capacity of composites.

strength gains observed at 0.1 wt% (compressive strength +8.4 %, flexural strength +14.0 %). Enhanced microcrack propagation mitigation and better interlocking of hydration products contributed to these improvements. Durability against moisture-induced deterioration was markedly improved, as evidenced by higher residual compressive strength and softening coefficients. Thermal properties were also enhanced due to reduced porosity and CNTox's intrinsic thermal conductivity.

Comparatively, MOC composites tolerated higher CNTox loadings with sustained mechanical and durability improvements, while PC composites showed sensitivity to CNTox dosage, with performance declining at higher contents. CNTox clustering was more prominent in MOC, likely contributing to superior microstructural interlocking and phase nucleation. Both materials benefited from CNTox's hydrophobic nature, which reduced moisture absorption and increased durability.

Overall, CNTox nano-reinforcement offers promising enhancements for both PC and MOC composites, with MOC displaying a more robust and sustained positive response. These findings support the tailored use of CNTox in cementitious materials to optimize mechanical performance, durability, and thermal functionality, advancing their potential in sustainable construction applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Adam Pivák: Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Milena Pavlíková:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Zbyšek Pavlík:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Adéla Jiříčková:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Ondřej Jankovský:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Anna-Marie Lauermannová:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Martina Záleská:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data statement

According to Open Science principles, raw data are available at DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15175334.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.cscm.2025.e04902](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscm.2025.e04902).

Data availability

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